

THE ROLE AND IMPACT TO THE EDUCATION QUALITY OF ICT

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ABSTRACT

This article purpose is highlights importance of the using information-communication technologies in the education and its impact to the education quality.

Keywords: education, education quality, modernization, information-communication technologies.

In the XX century, the scientific and technological revolution began, which brought many innovations in all spheres of human activity, including in the field of education. By the beginning of the XXI century, many business processes and relationships began to be built on the basis of information and communication technologies, including those based on Internet services and social networks.

Currently, modern youth actively communicates through social networks, gains new knowledge and improves their skills through open online courses, finds new promising areas for development and cooperation, remotely communicates with the employer and sends the results of work through e-mail. Young scientists and researchers (including students) are increasingly finding the materials and publications they need not in the libraries and periodicals, but on the global Internet (moreover, quickly and possibly volumetricly).

Despite the importance of information technologies for the development of trainees' personal qualities, their implementation should be implemented not so much by an extensive method, leading to an increase in both the academic load of students and teachers, and the total Expenditure on education, but rather by bringing the structure of education in line with modern goals.

The main goal of ICT is to ensure the modern quality of education on the basis of preserving its fundamental nature and compliance with the current and future needs of an individual, society, and the state. ICT objectives:

- increase learning motivation;
- improve the efficiency of the learning process;
- contribute to the activation of the cognitive sphere of students;
- improve methods of conducting classes;
- timely monitor the results of training and education;
- plan and organize your work;

- use as a means of self-education;
- prepare a lecture (event) qualitatively and quickly.

Benefits of using ICT:

- individualization of learning;
- Intensification of students' independent work;
- increase in the volume of tasks performed during the practical lesson;
- expansion of information flows when using the Internet;

The world around us is changing so quickly that the curricula for these changes often do not have time, and then the traditional structure of teaching academic disciplines can no longer meet the goals of education. By themselves, such skills are very important and useful - as a certain foundation of those aspects of future professional activity that are characterized by well-established traditional approaches. The use of information technologies ensures the intensification and actualization of the educational process by solving such basic tasks:

- identification and use of incentives to enhance cognitive activity through the use of various information technologies, selected depending on the type of personality of the student;

- deepening of interdisciplinary connections in solving problems from various subject areas through the use of modern information processing tools such as computer modeling, technologies of local and network databases and knowledge;

- trainee's active participation in the design and further updating of its educational trajectory, which provides a student-centered approach to the organization of the learning process.

ICTs expand the possibilities of the educational environment, both by a variety of software tools and methods for developing students' creativity. Such software includes modeling programs, search, intellectual training, expert systems, programs for conducting business games. In fact, all modern electronic textbooks emphasize the development of creative thinking. To this end, they offer tasks of a heuristic, creative nature, raise questions that cannot be answered unambiguously, etc. Communication technologies allow for a new way to implement methods that activate creative activity. Trainees can join in discussions that are held not only in the classroom, but also virtually, for example, on the websites of periodicals, training centers. Students of various educational institutions can participate in the implementation of joint creative projects. Information and communication technologies have an impact on the process of teaching and educating learners, students, and listeners, as they change the transmission patterns of knowledge and teaching methods. Implementation of information and communication technologies not only affects educational technologies, but also entails new ones. They are related to the use of computers and

telecommunications, specialized equipment, software and hardware, and information processing systems.

Unfortunately, today's observation of educational process in educational institutions indicates that the use of information and communication technologies remains incompatible with the rapid development in this area. This is due to the lack of material and technical base in some educational institutions, limited access to modern communication systems in some educational institutions, and the inefficient use of these opportunities in all educational institutions. In most cases, it is possible to observe that educational institutions are limited to preparing presentations for lecturers and teachers, and have become accustomed to unilateral use of information and communication facilities. Even with Microsoft's Windows applications, including the use of Microsoft Office software, it is down the road. The use of computer equipment in the learning process has led to the creation of a new generation of information technologies, the quality of education, the creation of new tools, and the effective collaboration between the teacher and the educator. According to experts, the new information-based educational technologies on the basis of computing tools provide a sufficient level of educational efficiency.

Application of ITO requires appropriate changes in the content of the studied discipline, the organization of activities of students and teachers, the establishment of special relations between them, implying greater autonomy and initiative of students, creating an atmosphere of cooperation between them and teachers. Informatization of education should not lead to its formalization. The teacher's time, released through the use of ITO, must be given to the student directly or indirectly through the creative growth of the teacher.

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